

MTU2009) and 5 levels of P (0, 17.5, 26.2, 35.0, and 43.7 kg/ha) applied basally as superphosphate. Before last puddling, 26.8 kg K₂O/ha was applied basally and 120 kg N/ha was applied in equal splits: basal, topdressing 25 d after planting, and before panicle initiation.

Grain and straw yields were statistical-

ly analyzed (see table). All treatments with added P gave higher grain yield than the control. Highest mean grain yield (5.3 t/ha) was from IR50, which was significantly superior to all other varieties (see table).

Mean grain yield for different P levels was significant only to 26.2 kg P/ha.

MTU6910 yielded more straw than all other varieties (see table). Varieties which recorded higher grain yield recorded low straw yield.

IR50 was best for rabi and application of 26.2 kg P/ha appeared to produce maximum yield for most rabi varieties. □

Optimum seeding rate and nitrogen level for rice grown in semidry conditions

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In Tamil Nadu almost 200,000 ha of semidry land is planted to rice. We sought to identify optimum seeding rate and nitrogen level for rice grown in semidry land in field trials at ACRI in 1978-79 and 1979-80.

Five seeding rates — 60, 80, 100, 120, and 140 kg seed/ha — and 4 nitrogen

levels — 0, 40, 80, and 120 kg N/ha — were evaluated in a split-plot design with 3 replications. Soil was sandy with pH 7.6, medium levels of available N and P, and low K.

Dry seed of MDU1, a 135-d variety recommended by Tamil Nadu Agricultural University for semidry conditions, was sown in lines and N was applied in 2 equal splits: at maximum tillering (25 d after transplanting) and at panicle initiation. The crop was grown under controlled water conditions until tillering, then irrigated like lowland rice. Butachlor 5% granules were applied at 1.5 kg

ai/ha 5 d after sowing to control weeds.

Data on grain yield and other components are in the table. Seeding rate did not significantly influence grain yield in 1978-79. In 1979-80 sowing, 100 kg seed/ha produced the highest yield — 1.8 t/ha. There was no significant difference between 80 kg and 100 kg seed/ha, however.

Nitrogen level increased grain yield significantly at the no-N vs N application level, but there was no significant difference between applications of 40, 80, and 120 kg. The most economic dose was 40 kg N/ha. □

Effect of seeding rate and nitrogen level on grain yield and yield components, Tamil Nadu, 1978-1980.

Treatment	1978-79				1979-80			
	Productive tillers (no.)	Grains/panicle	1,000-grain wt (g)	Yield (t/ha)	Productive tillers (no.)	Grains/panicle	1,000-grain wt (g)	Yield (t/ha)
<i>Seeding rate (kg/ha)</i>								
60	5.5	64.4	21.2	0.7	6.3	66.4	21.2	1.2
80	5.8	63.8	21.3	1.0	6.6	69.0	21.8	1.6
100	5.5	58.7	21.2	0.9	6.3	59.5	20.8	1.8
120	4.9	52.5	20.8	0.6	5.3	51.4	20.4	1.0
140	5.3	56.2	20.9	0.7	5.7	55.2	21.2	1.1
<i>Nitrogen level (kg/ha)</i>								
0	4.1	53.9	20.8	0.6	4.4	58.3	20.8	0.8
40	6.4	58.7	20.8	0.8	7.1	59.2	20.8	1.5
80	5.6	61.8	21.2	0.9	6.3	62.3	21.5	1.6
120	5.4	62.3	21.4	0.9	6.2	61.4	21.6	1.5
SE								
Seeding rate	0.4	7.5	0.83	1.4	0.41	5.6	0.23	173
Nitrogen level	0.2	4.8	0.2	0.32	3.5	0.12	0.1	
CD (0.05)								
Seeding rate	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	0.4
Nitrogen level	0.5	ns	ns	0.2	0.65	ns	0.24	0.3

Effect of calcium peroxide-coated rice seeds on germination and seedling growth under submerged conditions

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Rice is direct seeded in rainfed lowlands in much of Asia and South Asia. Sudden heavy rain often submerges the seeded fields, and greatly affects germination and seedling emergence.

We studied the effect of coating rice

seeds with calcium peroxide on germination and seedling establishment under submerged conditions. NC492 and Jaladhi 2 seeds were coated with 20% and 40% calcium peroxide by weight. Five seeds were sown in each 6-cm-diam

plastic pot and 20 pots comprised each of 5 replications in a randomized block design. Another experiment used 10.5-cm-diam petri plates in the laboratory. In each plate, 100 seeds were placed on filter paper and 2 ml of distilled water was added. Each set was in three replications.

The pots were submerged, leaving seeds 10 cm below water level for 5 d in controlled tanks. Then the water level was reduced to 2 cm and maintained for 15 d, after which data were recorded.

Results of the pot experiment showed that 40% coating significantly increased the percentage germination for both cultivars (Table 1).

Results of the petri plate test indicated germination and seedling growth of both cultivars was reduced at both calcium peroxide concentrations (Table 2) perhaps because an alkaline medium developed from the solution of calcium peroxide in water. Further study is in progress. □

Table 1. Effect of calcium peroxide coating on germination of two rice cultivars under submerged conditions, Chinsurah, India.^a

Treatment	Germination ^b (%)	Mean shoot length (cm)	Mean root length (cm)
<i>NC492</i>			
CaO ₂ coated (40%)	86.6**	25.0	14.8
CaO ₂ coated (20%)	70.0**	23.3	14.1
Uncoated (dry)	16.6	24.2	12.8
Uncoated (sprouted)	35.0	23.9	13.0
<i>Jaladhi 2</i>			
CaO ₂ coated (40%)	73.3**	22.1	16.8
CaO ₂ coated (20%)	68.3 *	20.9	14.0
Uncoated (dry)	56.6	16.6	12.7
Uncoated (sprouted)	60.6	18.4	13.4

^aData were recorded 20 d after sowing. ^b*Significant at P = 0.05, **significant at P = 0.01.

Table 2. Effect of calcium peroxide coating on germination of two rice cultivars in petri plates in the laboratory, Chinsurah, India.^a

Treatment	Germination (%)	Mean shoot length (cm)	Mean root length (cm)
<i>NC492</i>			
CaO ₂ coated (40%)	62.0	7.2	3.5
CaO ₂ coated (20%)	69.0	11.2	6.5
Uncoated	100.0	14.6	11.5
<i>Juladhi 2</i>			
CaO ₂ coated (40%)	59.0	6.2	5.0
CaO ₂ coated (20%)	76.0	7.5	5.2
Uncoated	98.0	13.2	14.5

^aData were recorded after 10 d.

Effect of seedling age at transplanting and fertilizer levels on grain yield

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We tested the performance of IR6 at different transplanting ages and 10 fertilizer levels at ARS and the Government Seed Farm Rakh Manghan in D. I. Khan in 1982. The experiment was in a split-plot design with three replications. Seedling ages were evaluated in main plots and fertility levels in subplots.

N, P, and K were broadcast and incorporated into dry soil before transplanting. A composite soil sample (0-25 cm) was analyzed (Table 1).

Grain yields for seedlings transplanted at different ages did not significantly differ (Table 2). Yield increased significantly as fertilizer levels were increased. The highest grain yield of 6.4 t/ha was obtained with 138-26-0 kg NPK/ha (Table 2). □

Table 1. Physicochemical properties of soils at two experimental sites in India.

Location	pH (1:5)	Exc10 ⁶ (1:5)	P (ppm)	K (ppm)	OM (%)	Texture
Agricultural Research Station	8.1	950	3	145	0.62	Clayey
Government Seed Farm Rakh Manghan	8.0	1200	2	124	0.72	Clayey

Table 2. Effect of seedling age and different fertilizer levels on rice (IR6) grain yield. D. I. Khan, NWFP, Pakistan, 1982.

Fertilizer applied (kg/ha)			Grain yield ^a (t/ha) of seedlings transplanted at			Av grain yield ^b (t/ha)
N	P	K	30 d	45 d	60 d	
0	0	0	3.4	3.6	2.9	3.3 f
46	0	0	4.5	4.8	4.5	4.6 e
92	0	0	5.4	5.4	5.4	5.4 bcd
138	0	0	6.3	6.3	5.9	6.7 ab
46	26	0	4.7	4.9	4.8	4.8 de
92	26	0	6.1	5.7	5.7	5.8 abc
138	26	0	6.9	6.4	6.0	6.4 a
46	26	50	4.5	5.3	4.9	4.9 cde
92	26	50	5.9	6.0	5.7	5.9 ab
138	26	50	5.8	6.2	6.2	6.1 ab
Average			5.3	5.5	5.2	

^aAv of 2 locations. ^b Means followed by a similar letter are not significantly different at 5% level.